

Corporate Innovation and Equity Value: A Case of Coronavirus Crisis

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Corporate innovation is one of the significant elements contributing to business performance and maintaining corporate competitive advantage. However, research conducted to examine the effect of innovation on equity value during normal business periods has produced mixed results. Hence, this research considers the contribution of corporate innovation towards equity value throughout the coronavirus crisis, to ascertain if the results during the pandemic period corroborate the results during the normal business period. This study adopted a quantitative technique to test the Dynamic Capabilities Theory. Non-primary data were extracted from the financial reports of selected international businesses ranked by Financial Times as thriving throughout the coronavirus times. The cross-sectional information spanning the years, 2019, 2020, and 2021. Employing ordinary least squares regression method, the findings show that innovation had a significant detrimental influence on the Tobin's Q during a pandemic. The findings are in line with other scholars who obtained an adverse association between corporate innovation and performance of businesses. The study is one of the first few studies to contribute to the innovation and equity value relationship research by addressing whether the positive impact exists during the coronavirus crisis using data from the best one hundred businesses prospering amid the pandemic. This study's findings may serve as a roadmap for future studies due to its cross-sectional quantitative approach.

Keywords: Corporate innovation, COVID-19 pandemic, dynamic capabilities theory, equity value, firm size

The outbreak of coronavirus disease of 2019 has resulted in a widespread public health emergency and an economic crisis, which caused a dramatic shift in how organisations operate and challenged the traditional standards of business strategy (Haque et al., 2025; Noone et al., 2022). This global phenomenon has necessitated transformed approaches to business to grow their market presence and customer base with the aim of maximising shareholder value. Moreover, the COVID-19 induced stringent lockdown measures impacted both the in store and online consumer purchasing behaviours and brought businesses' capacity to respond and innovate under pressure (Maalouf et al., 2025; Rose et al., 2023).

Surprisingly, the coronavirus outbreak re-energised the debate regarding the influence of crisis on business performance amongst academics and practitioners (Läger et al., 2025). Many prior studies have examined the effect of external business threats, such as epidemics, natural disasters and economic recession, on financial performance. These studies found that, for example, amid the outbreaks of bovine spongiform encephalopathy (BSE), severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS), Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV), the 2008 worldwide economic downturn and the COVID-19 pandemic, sales revenues declined significantly (Shen et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2009; Notta & Vlachvei, 2014) and firm values were negatively affected (Hadi et al., 2020; Zopiatis et al., 2019; Overby et al., 2004).

Analysing the effect of a dramatic shift in business operation and consumer behaviours on firm performances during the COVID-19 crisis, scholars document contrasting effects (Valaskova et al., 2023; Fairlie & Fossen, 2022; Mohammad, 2025). Some companies (including Macdonald's, Amazon, Microsoft, & Apple) not only stayed afloat but flourished with "unprecedented" sales surges, and substantially increased their equity values (Han, 2021) while some were merely resilient. The market capitalisation added during the pandemic for Amazon, Microsoft, and Apple was respectively \$401.1bn, \$269.9bn, and \$219.1bn (Financial Times, 2020). According to the Financial Times (2020), companies that innovated in response to the pandemic survived as a result (Financial Times, 2020). However, these corporate winners' secrets of survival and ability to achieve their corporate goals during the COVID-19 pandemic have remained elusive/hidden, and unavailable to mainstream media or academic researchers. This reason motivated this study: to probe deeper into the secrets that enabled these corporate winners to succeed even during a period of global adversity. Hence, the paper investigates the effect of firm innovation

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on the equity value of multinational companies during a pandemic, such as the coronavirus.

Based on the Global Innovation Index 2021 and Sung and Kim (2021) innovation has been the crucial tool that propels organizations to attain a competitive advantage and to survive and prosper. A recent research examining the influence of coronavirus on innovation reveals that innovation significantly impacts business performance (Sudjatmoko et al., 2023). Innovation is often associated with the introduction of something new (Erkut, 2020). Innovation refers to any idea, process, product, system, or device considered new by an individual, organisation, or society, highlighting its role in driving change and value creation (Vakola & Rezgui, 2000). The OECD defines innovation as developing an advanced product or marketing method, or process or commercial practices in a new way of doing business (OECD & Eurostat, 2005, s46).

Several authors like Bogetoft et al. (2024) and Ortiz and Gargallo-Castel (2025) agree that corporate innovation is crucial for improving firm performance across many industries, as it allows firms to respond to changes in competition, technology, and market opportunities through the creation of innovative products, systems and techniques. Ortiz and Gargallo-Castel (2025) explained that corporate innovation, consequently, contributes to economic value creation and is instrumental in securing an advantageous position.

The subject of corporate innovation and its effect on equity values has been investigated extensively but not profoundly. Observation suggests that businesses are catalytic instruments that create opportunities for sustainable and inclusive economic growth in the worldwide economy (Stundziene et al., 2024; Matenda & Sibanda, 2023). In view of the economic and societal benefits that may grow from corporate innovation and equity value, these two concepts have been debated about amongst researchers, practitioners and policy makers. Nonetheless, the corporate innovation and prior studies on firm value have predominantly concentrated on direct effects of innovation within a pre-crisis setting, the mediating and moderating roles of innovation, on sectors within one country, in developing and developed country contexts (see, for instance, Haque et al., 2025; Fainshtein et al., 2024; Liu, 2024; Ortiz & Gargallo-Castel, 2025; Zehir & Vural, 2025).

However, limited research has examined the impact of innovation on firm equity value within the coronavirus crisis exclusively (Nathan & Rosso, 2022). More so, previous researchers' conclusions and recommendations are conflicting, thereby providing little guidance on the influence of innovation on a firm's equity value particularly during a COVID-19 crisis (Bogetoft et al., 2024; Henao-García et al., 2024; Fatema & Islam, 2023; Zhu et al., 2025). There is little to show regarding the examinations of corporate innovation focusing exclusively on the top 100 global business amid coronavirus period, as a unit of study.

Even so, studying the influence of innovation initiatives on equity value under crisis conditions is of significant scholarly relevance (Haque et al., 2025). Thus, extending research on the impact of innovation on firm value nexus throughout the coronavirus period will shed light on how prospectors, defenders, and analyser firms, as classified by Miles, Snow, Meyer, and Coleman (1978) were able to employ innovation activities to adapt during turbulent times to stimulate firms' competitive advantage, which leads to superior performance.

From the identified research problem, we formulated the research question as: What effect does corporate innovation have on the equity value of the best 100 global businesses that thrived amid the coronavirus crisis? In line with the research question, this paper seeks to assess the impact of firm innovation on the equity value of best 100 businesses that flourished amid the coronavirus period.

We use the dynamic capabilities theory (DCT) of competitive advantage as theoretical lens for this study, specifically appropriate in rapidly changing environments (Teece et al., 1997). According to DCT, firms can promote a sustainable competitive advantage over their rivals by adapting, innovating, and transforming their internal resources and capabilities. Moreover, the DCT suggests that by adapting their innovation resources, firms will attain superior performance, especially in the course of the coronavirus pandemic (Jingwen et al., 2025).

To comprehend the role of corporate innovation on the value of firms amid the coronavirus period, the research employs the ordinary least squares multivariate technique to analyse the cross-sectional data from 74 global companies that thrived around the coronavirus crisis. The cross-sectional data were collected during the period 2019-2021. The regression suggests that innovation does not enhance the equity value of the performance of global businesses that demonstrated resilience and success through the coronavirus period.

This paper contributes to three aspects. Firstly, this paper adds to the body of literature that has examined the impact of environmental jolts, such as the global COVID-19 pandemic and associated financial crisis, on firms' performance. As far as the researchers are aware, research exploring the effects of a pandemic on firms' innovation and equity value during such an abnormal period is still very limited. Secondly, based on the data from the top 100 companies around the world, this paper offers international evidence on the effect of innovation on equity value during a crisis. Unlike prior studies that focused on a single country or firm level (Abbas et al., 2024; Noone et al., 2024). Finally, following Henao-García et al. (2024) call, this study used a widely considered and respected organisational theory (a theory that is almost inevitably a dominant part of current conversations among academics & practitioners) to explore the relationship between superior performance and a firm's use of its resources and capabilities during a pandemic.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides theoretical grounding and the empirical background. Section 3 provides an overview of data and research methodology. Results and analyses are described in Section 4. The study is concluded in Section 5.

Review of Literature

Teece et al. (1997) were the first to argue that businesses achieve competitive advantage and variation in profits by effectively reconfiguring internal capabilities and resources under conditions of uncertainty, and they introduced the dynamic capabilities framework as an extension of the resource-based view (Fainshtein et al., 2024). According to Teece et al. (1997), competitive edge arises when a firm adopts a value-creating strategy that is unique and not currently employed by any existing or potential rivals. From the core of dynamic capabilities theory, it is clear that the resources that once met the Valuable, Rare, Inimitable, and Non-substitutable (VRIN) criteria as the source of competitive advantage, could suddenly become obsolete in highly dynamic and uncertain environments

(Teece et al., 1997). This suggests that firms must take advantage of opportunities in the fast-changing commercial setting and continuously convert their resources to preserve their competitive advantage (Maalouf et al., 2025).

Since the studies by Griliches (1980) cited in Griliches and Lichtenberg (1984) numerous scholars have confirmed that innovation has a positive (negative) effect on firms' economic outcomes. Building on the principles of upper echelon theory, Erhan et al. (2024) investigated the association between innovation and organizational performance during the coronavirus pandemic context using Indonesia Stock Exchange -listed firms. Erhan et al. (2024) reported that firms that pursued innovation experienced higher equity value amid the coronavirus period. Öztaş and Öztaş (2024) explored the innovation performance of G20 countries, which account for approximately over 75% of the global trade, based on multi-criteria-decision-making techniques and to understand whether the coronavirus pandemic has affected the innovation performance of the countries and found that innovation was associated with growth during the COVID-19 pandemic. Maingehama (2025) finds that innovation is a crucial factor for the growth trajectories of South African SME's. Building on the conceptual basis established by Miles et al. (1978) and a sample of 138 publicly listed international companies, Poretti et al. (2024) provide evidence that more innovative business strategies lead to higher market valuations. Similar results were also reported by Praditya and Purwanto (2024), Vo et al. (2025), Liu (2024), Kyaw et al. (2025), and Noone et al. (2024) who demonstrate a positive and significant connection between innovation capabilities and competitive edge, consistent with Teece et al.'s explanation.

Petrescu et al. (2025) examined whether innovation is a driver of firm value in Western Europe amid multiple crises triggered by the coronavirus. The sample included firms in various sectors. The findings reveal adverse results for firms in the energy, chemicals and pharmaceutical sectors. Conversely, a statistically significant positive association was observed on the influence of research and development on the firm performance of high-technology industry.

Moreover, using 60 German publicly traded corporations' data, Menter et al. (2023) show that innovation lagged positive effect on firm value. Restrepo-Morales et al. (2024) investigated how Latin American SME's navigate the economic challenges caused by

coronavirus. Restrepo-Morales et al. (2024) results reveal that innovation adversely influenced the competitive performance in periods of uncertainty.

Haque et al. (2025) focused on a selection of firms in the United States and empirical analyse whether a firm's innovative business strategy assists in mitigating the extent of a pandemic crisis on its performance. They found that the sampled firms with innovative strategies suffered a decrease in performance over the course of the coronavirus pandemic in comparison to firms with non-innovative strategies. Likewise, the association of innovation and performance of Bombay Stock Exchange-listed technology-focused firms was analysed by Chatterjee and Bhattacharjee (2021) using Tobin's Q as the non-independent variable. Innovation was measured by the firm's R&D investment. The control variables included in the study were firm age, size and the debt-to-asset ratio. Hypothesis testing was conducted through ordinary least squares (OLS) regression. The authors found that innovation does not influence the firm's value.

In summary, prior literature has identified that, to maintain a competitive advantage during turbulent times and address rapidly changing environments, firms need to create, expand, and integrate. And reconfigure the innovation capabilities. However, there was no consensus that corporate innovation can drive firms' sustained equity value. Accordingly, we expect corporate innovation to influence the equity value of companies amid the coronavirus period. Which forms the basis for the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis of the Study

H1. Firm equity value around the coronavirus crisis can significantly improve due to innovation.

Method

The study adopted a quantitative technique to test existing theory and measure variables through statistical techniques. The data set encompasses best 100 firms worldwide that succeeded through the coronavirus pandemic (Financial Times 2020). This research examines the timeframe from 2019 to 2021(COVID period). The financial statements of the sampled firms were used to obtain reliable data. Excluding 26 companies due to incomplete data, the eventual data set comprised 74 firms as reported in Table 1. Thus, the analytical unit for this study is the individual companies prospering during the COVID-19 pandemic, at the individual firm level.

Table 1

Population and Sample

Sector number	Sector	Total companies	%	Total companies	%
1	Communication services	10	10%	9	12%
2	Consumer discretionary	21	21%	12	16%
3	Consumer staples	8	8%	4	5%
4	Energy	2	2%	1	1%
5	Financials	1	1%	Excluded	Excluded
6	Health	25	25%	22	30%
7	Materials	6	6%	3	4%
8	Real estate	5	5%	2	3%
9	Technology	23	23%	21	28%
		100	100%	74	100%

To assess the impact of firm innovation on equity value throughout coronavirus period, we use the ordinary least squares multivariate

regression technique with cross sectional data. The cross-sectional data analysis was used to achieve this paper's empirical objective so

as to obtain data at a specific period of coronavirus. In contrast to panel data analysis, a cross-sectional technique quantifies the association between explanatory variables and firm outcome at a specific period of the coronavirus. The model for this study is stated as:

$$\text{Tobin } Q_i = \alpha + \beta_1 CIn_i + \beta' x'_i + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

Where Tobin Q_i represents the equity value for company i. CIn represents the corporate innovation, and x' represents the vector of control variables, namely firm leverage, age of the firm, size of the firm and marketing expenses. α is an intercept and ε stands for the error term.

Six constructs were evaluated in this paper: Tobin-Q, Corporate Innovation, Firm Size, Marketing Expenses, Firm Age and Leverage. Corporate performance evaluation is even more vital in a dynamic market environment such as during the global COVID-19 pandemic, as it is used to measure if a company's resources are being efficiently and effectively used (Nuta et al., 2025). As a “financial return the company receives in each year of operation” (Gallego-Álvarez et al., 2014, p. 365) it can be measured using both accounting and market-based metrics (Läger et al., 2025). Following Venkatraman and Ramanujam (1986) we employ a market-based measure of equity value in the form of Tobin's Q, broadly used in strategic management literature. Tobin's Q is measured as the firm's enterprise value divided by the book value of its assets (Läger et al., 2025). Chen et al. (2021) indicated that, while accounting-based measures may capture immediate impacts, they are influenced by the accounting practices adopted by the firms and are found to be a biased reflection of performance.

To measure corporate innovation, this study employed the research and development expenditure. Corporate innovation is expected to be a crucial factor in supporting the sales revenues and

equity values of firms prospering during the coronavirus crisis. Most literature concentrating on the determinants of firms' superior performance has employed R&D expenditure as a proxy for corporate innovation. Such studies include those of (Liu, 2024; & Petrescu et al., 2025).

This study considers the following firm characteristics as control variables that have a possible influence on Tobin's Q: (i) the total assets (Firm Size), (ii) marketing expenses (ME), (iii) firm age (FA), and (iv) debt-to-asset ratio (Lev). The control variables will likely mitigate possible omitted variable prejudice and endogeneity included in a regression. The researchers limited the control variables to those most commonly found in the innovation literature. Firm size (FS) is assessed by the logarithm of total assets. Prasasti et al. (2025) found that big businesses exploit the scale economies, hence they have superior performance than smaller firms.

On the contrary, Alabdullah et al. (2018) found that firm size does not matter. Mirza, Hussain, and Gull (2022) and Kanellos et al. (2025) among other scholars, have found that high levels of marketing expenditure led to increased firm value. Leverage (LEV), proxied by a firm's long-term debt divided by total assets. Leverage may affect the firm's ability to finance investment activities (Läger et al., 2025; Liu, 2024). A firm age (FAG), measured as the current year minus the firm's commencement year are other variables included as control variables. The empirical studies that have employed these measures include those of Setiawan and Septiani (2025), Liu et al. (2025), Kyaw et al. (2025), Zehir and Vural (2025), Läger et al. (2025), and Haque et al. (2025). The current study expected firm size, marketing expenses, firm age, and leverage to have a favorable impact on equity values in line with prior studies.

A summary of the proxies that were used to measure all the variables and their sources of data is shown in Table 2.

Table 2
Variables, Proxies and Data Bases

Variables	Symbol	Explanation	Bases
Tobin-Q	Tobin-Q	Tobin's Q refers to the market value of equity/ book value of assets	AR
Leverage	Lev	Firms' total liabilities/total equity	AR
Firm Size	FS	Total of the value of assets	AR
Firm Age	FA	Present year minus firm's formation year	AR
Marketing Expenses	ME	Marketing expenses refers to selling, marketing and distribution costs	AR
Corporate Innovation	CIn	Research and development expenditure is used to measure corporate innovation	AR

Note. AR = Annual reports of sampled companies

Results

Data analysis was performed using the rcorr function within R's Hmisc package. Descriptive statistics for the predictive and explanatory variables of the current study are presented in Table 3 for the 74 firms that prospered during the COVID-19 pandemic, by using the mean, minimum, standard deviation and maximum statistics. In Table 3, reports summary statistics of the firm, age, firm size, leverage, marketing expenses and Tobin's Q. The mean of the selling and administrative expenses was US\$ 7 355.77 million. The average firm age is 36.27 years, where the youngest firms had been operating for five years to those with up to 154 years in operation. Innovation averages US\$ 4 521.99 million, while Tobin's Q average was US\$ 642.26. The mean of firm leverage was 0.54.

The correlations among the study variables, calculated using Pearson's method, are presented in Table 4. The interrelationship of innovation and equity value, measured by Tobin's Q, is negative and statistically significant at the 0.001 level of confidence. In addition, leverage, firm size and marketing expenses exhibit a negative and statistically significant association with Tobin Q, whereas firm age shows a strong, favorable correlation with Tobin's Q. Of note is that highly correlated variables, with a correlation coefficient of at least 0.8, are thought to cause multicollinearity in regression analyses (Gregorich et al., 2021). The correlation results show that only one relationship is highly correlated: marketing expenses and corporate innovation (0.80). However, a variance inflation factor (VIF) assessment was conducted and findings in Table 5 reveal that there are no multicollinearity issues.

Table 3*Descriptive Statistics*

Variables	N	M	Std dev	Med	Minimum	Maimumx	Std E
Tobin-Q	74	642.26	3184.10	5.64	0.09	23963.60	370.14
Size	74	80977.36	196398.84	21799.75	49.93	1320000.00	22830.90
Marketing	74	7355.77	17286.24	1245.00	4.98	124000.00	2009.48
Age	74	36.27	35.27	22	5	154	4.10
Leverage	74	0.54	0.26	0.51	0.00	1.31	0.03
Corporate innovation	74	4521.92	9850.15	1234.70	1.12	51865.00	1145.06

Note. firm size, marketing expenses, and corporate innovation proxies indicates United States (US) million dollars. N = number of observations; M = mean; std dev = standard deviation; Med = Median; Std E = standard error.

Table 4*Correlation Analysis*

Variable	Tobin-Q	FS	ME	FA	Lev	CI
Tobin-Q	1					
FS	-0.29***	1				
ME	-0.42***	0.7***	1			
FA	0.36***	0.05	-0.2*	1		
Lev	-0.31***	-0.16	0.25**	-0.13	1	
CIn	-0.42***	0.59***	0.80***	-0.13	0.15	1

Note. Statistical significance at the 1%,5%, and 10% levels is indicated by ***, ** and * respectively, and all variables are logarithmically transformed. FS = Firm size; ME = Marketing expenses; FA = Firm Age; Lev = Leverage; CIn = Corporate Innovation.

Table 5*Multicollinearity Test*

Variables	VIF
Firm size	4.489
Marketing expenses	2.670
Firm age	1.119
Leverage	1.375
Corporate innovation	2.772

Note. The VIF values < 5 indicate that multicollinearity is likely not a concern.

The Pearson correlation matrix presents a preliminary overview of variable interrelationships. As a result, this study conducts the OLS analysis for cross-sectional data to further establish the impact of corporate innovation on equity value, and controls for other supporting variables, as shown in Equation 1. This analysis is carried out in Table 6.

The fundamental expectations of linear regression models have been met, as shown by the pre-estimation tests in Table 6 and plots on Figure 1 and 2. Table 6 results are also robust to multicollinearity, as indicated in Table 5. The robustness tests regarding heteroscedasticity, multicollinearity and auto correlations were done as per Table 5 and Table 6. Additionally, the pre-estimation plots listed on Figure 1 and 2 confirm that the data met the linear regression assumption requirements.

Table 6 provides the findings on the cross-sectional regression inquiry of the impact of corporate innovation on equity value during COVID-19. Tobin Q is employed to determine equity value, while corporate innovation serves as the key independent variable. The

Table 6*Cross-sectional Regression Analysis: Impact of Corporate Innovation on Equity Value*

Dependent variable:	Tobin's Q	
	Coefficient	Standard errors
Intercept	9.722***	(3.092)
Corporate innovation	-0.287*	(0.172)
Marketing expenses	0.137	(0.226)
Firm size	-0.345*	(0.201)
Firm age	0.891***	(0.291)
Leverage	-0.721***	(0.278)
N	74	
Adj. R2	0.299	
F-stats	7.215	
Pval	<0.001	
Diagnostics tests		
Autocorrelation		
Breusch-Godfrey (BG) test for serial correlation	2.73	
Pval	0.06	
Heteroscedasticity		
studentized Breusch-Pagan (BP) test	8.80	
Pval	0.16	

Note. The symbols*** and * denote statistical significance levels at the 0.01 and 0.1 levels, respectively. Standard errors are reported in parentheses. The null hypotheses of the Breusch-Pagan (BP) and Breusch-Godfrey (BG) tests are that the model residuals exhibit homoscedasticity and no autocorrelation, respectively. Accordingly, a p-value greater than 0.005 indicates that the null hypotheses of homoscedasticity and absence of autocorrelation cannot be rejected, N is number of observations, Pval is the p-value

Figure 1
Diagnostic Plots for Objective 5 Specification

Figure 2
Normality and Autocorrelation Tests of Objective 5 Specification

model also includes firm size, firm age, leverage and marketing expenses as control variables. The empirical results demonstrate that the estimated coefficient of corporate innovation is statistically significant, implying that if listed companies increased their investment in corporate innovation by 1% during the COVID-19 period, their equity value would have declined by 0.29%, which does not support H1. Firms' ages, on the other hand, increased the firms' value of equity during the coronavirus period. Nonetheless, firm size and leverage have a negative and statistically significant effect on equity value, with coefficients of 0.345 and 0.721 respectively. This implies that increasing the firm's size and leveraging during the coronavirus period presented an adverse effect on their equity values. The estimated coefficient of the marketing expense variable is statistically insignificant, implying that marketing expenditure had no significant impact on the equity value of the listed firms during the COVID-19 period.

Discussion

Like the correlation results in Table 4, the cross-sectional regression results in Table 6 indicate that corporate innovation significantly and negatively influenced Tobin's Q during COVID-19. The findings contradict the dynamic capabilities (Teece et al., 1997) which

predicted that innovation would increase a firm's equity value and send a positive signal to investors, who expect value creation from investing in firms in the form of sustained profits (Wang, 2011). This means that corporate innovation is perceived to be a cost, which reduces firms' operating performance and does not quickly compensate investors. Thus, it is not a resource to create the firm's competitive advantage and sustained growth during a crisis.

The statistically significant and negative findings contradict recent studies such as those of Erhan et al. (2024), Bogetoft et al. (2024), and Ortiz and Gargallo-Castel (2025) who reported that corporate innovation has a significant and positive relationship with Tobin's Q, and argue that internal research capabilities are critical to a firm's ability to generate superior outcomes during a crisis period. The findings are in line with Restrepo-Morales et al. (2024), Chatterjee and Bhattacharjee (2021), and Petrescu et al. (2025) who documented an adverse connection between corporate innovation and business performance.

The inverse connection could be attributable to the fact that most firms had no experience in dealing with failure brought about by the COVID-19 crisis and its effect on the global business ecosystem and were therefore focusing on surviving the crisis and minimizing their financial distress. Additionally, Viglioni et al. (2022) reasoned that

the fact that corporate innovation is associated with a decline in firm equity value refutes the view that firms do not require additional time to demonstrate adequate returns on corporate innovation investments. Thus, according to Noone et al. (2022), corporate innovation as a crisis-response mechanism may contribute significantly to the firm's survival and competitive capacity only at the end of the slowdown.

Notably, the statistically significant and negative correlation between corporate innovation and Tobin's Q contradicts the strong and highly significant association between corporate innovation and sales revenue. However, the observed discrepancy reinforces the contention that financial statement-based and market-based metrics reflect different dimensions of performance outcomes of firms and can be influenced differently by identical activities (Venkatraman & Ramanujam, 1986).

Conclusion

This paper examined the impact of innovation on equity value amid the coronavirus pandemic, using cross-sectional data covering 74 firms over the period of 2019 to 2021. The analysis demonstrates a statistically significant inverse connection between corporate innovation and Tobin's Q. The estimated coefficient of corporate innovation shows that, when listed companies increased their investment in corporate innovation by 1% during COVID-19, their equity value declined by 0.29%. Additionally, firm age was found to have a direct impact on equity value. The inverse relationship could be attributable to the fact that most firms had no experience in dealing with failure brought about by the coronavirus crisis and its influence on the global business ecosystem and were therefore focusing on surviving the crisis and minimizing their financial distress. The study suggests that investment in innovation did not meaningfully enhance the value of firms' equity amid the coronavirus period. However, investment in innovation may be considered a point of departure when evaluating the strategic deployment of resources to enhance performance outcomes.

The study advances the literature by its empirical assessment of the resourcefulness of corporate innovation on equity value amid the coronavirus crisis using data from international non-financial listed firms, unlike most of the prior studies, which used firms in a single industry and country, which do not depict the picture of the global economy. Our study provides important implications for corporate innovation research. First, this study suggests that business leaders should work towards creating a favourable environment for research and development to improve processes, develop new products and adapt to turbulent markets. Second, this study has contributed to academic theory by employing a renowned organisational theory - dynamic capabilities theory- to evaluate the influence of environmental jolts (such as the global financial crises, SARS, etc.) on firm performance, which is an aspect that has not been thoroughly explored. According to the current understanding, research on strategic resources and capabilities, and equity value during a pandemic, are few in number, and this study is one of the first empirical studies.

This research is subject to specific limitations, which can be explored in future studies. First, innovation includes various instruments, such as product innovation, process innovation, and marketing innovation; however, this paper has not examined these instruments in detail. Future studies could investigate the

differentiated effects of various innovation types on a firm's equity value. Second, the analysis is confined to a sample consisting of a small portion of the entire population of global companies; however, the researchers are confident that the data obtained does provide an appropriate setting and realistic reflection of the situation guiding corporate winners during a pandemic crisis. Thus, it would be useful for future studies to extend the research to other regions and/or industries, particularly in technology and industry in an emerging economy or manufacturing sector, as the influence of the coronavirus pandemic on individual industries and the various authorities' reactions to the pandemic differed widely between industries and countries, and these may affect future research findings.

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